

Identifying Affective Gameplay Behaviors: How Video Games Help People Feel Better

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ABSTRACT

Video games provide excellent opportunities for people to manage their emotional well-being in everyday settings. In this study, the research team explores how video game players use games to regulate their moods and enhance their emotional and mental well-being to understand affective gameplay needs and behaviors. Using an online focus group study method, ten video game players' gameplay behaviors and needs were investigated. Findings suggest that repetitive and meditative gameplay mechanics, in-game trophies and the availability of achievements, overall world-building and narrative aspects of the game, and the number of players supported by the game are important elements in supporting individual players' various affective needs. The current study suggests that providing more options for selections and searches in retrieval and recommendation services to video game players would be helpful in satisfying their diverse affective needs.

KEYWORDS

Video games; Emotion regulation; Focus group; Recommendation services; Information behavior; Mental health

INTRODUCTION

The importance of everyday media entertainment use has been researched in a positive light to support the general public's emotional well-being (Reinecke & Riege, 2020). However, empirical studies investigating which elements and features in entertainment media may be critical in regulating emotions are still lacking. Video games have unique interactive format characteristics, which make them uniquely suited to be used as tools to deal with emotional and mental health challenges. The current study hypothesizes that video game players use video games as tools to actively cope with their everyday life emotional struggles, ranging from mild stress to more severe conditions, such as anxiety or depression. However, current mainstream video game search and recommendation services do not provide search features for users to choose games based on emotional and mental needs. This lack of information and functionality not only hinders users' overall search experiences and joy of media consumption, but unexpected narrative elements may also act as triggers for users with particular emotional and mental needs. To address this problem, this study aims to 1) observe how people play games to regulate their moods and 2) understand their affective needs and game-playing behaviors in everyday life. In order to achieve these goals, the following research questions are investigated:

- **RQ1:** How do people play video games to feel better?
- **RQ2:** What aspects of gameplay experiences help people feel better?

Findings from this study contribute to the media entertainment resilience models and expand the understanding of information needs and behavior theories. In addition, our research team envisions that the findings of this study will help information professionals understand video game users' affective/emotional needs and contribute to enhancing the current video game recommendations and reference services to be more rigorous and inclusive.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The research team adopts concepts from bibliotherapy to video games. Bibliotherapy is a form of creative therapy used in both formal therapeutic settings to support the treatment of mental or psychological disorders. It is also sometimes used in libraries to connect readers to helpful resources. Bibliotherapy has been used to help people who experience PTSD (Glavin & Montgomery, 2017), depression, or anxiety (Peterkin & Gerwal, 2017). In addition to books and poems, now mental health professionals utilize comic books in counseling and bibliotherapy, especially with younger generations (Lee *et al.*, 2012; Rubin, 2020).

Similar to bibliotherapy, there has been an increasing body of research on video games that emphasizes the emotionally resilient aspects of playing video games. Reinecke and Riege (2020), for example, suggest the Recovery and Resilience in the Entertaining Media Use Model (R²EM-Model). Their model illustrates how interactive media facilitate recovery from stress; it identifies short-term recovery factors, such as Psychological Detachment and Relaxation, and long-term resiliency factors, such as Positive Emotions, Self-efficacy, Social Support, and more. Reinecke and Riege's conceptualization of emotional recovery with the help of interactive media echoes the findings of Sonnentag and Fritz (2007), which emphasize how enjoying hobbies (off-job activities) is associated with stress recovery.

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Similarly, Gross (2014) discusses a strategic distraction that active engagement with leisure activities, such as video games, can provide. Patel and colleagues' study (2006) on the positive influences of hand-held video games in decreasing preoperative anxiety and the findings from Russoniello *et al.* (2013) that casual gameplay may decrease depression symptoms also echo this claim. While these "distractions" can be achieved either through active involvement like playing video games, or passive activities such as reading or watching (Dahlquist *et al.*, 2009), the current study aims to focus on the first—active involvement with video games—as an everyday emotion regulation method.

METHODS

The current study used a focus group method as a pilot study for a larger research project. The focus group sessions' leading questions and discussion points were created based on the existing models on interactive media use and emotional resilience (Gross, 2014; Reinecke & Riege, 2020; Sonnentag & Fritz, 2007), and the research team intended to allow participants freely talk about their experiences that may not be direct answers to the questions and discussion points. Once Institutional Review Board (IRB) approved the research plan, the research team recruited participants for the focus group sessions who were 18 years old or older and enjoyed video games as a hobby. The recruitment was conducted via the student e-mail listserv at the University of Missouri in October 2022. Two groups of five participants each were recruited for the focus group sessions to create a small, comfortable environment where participants could share their gameplay behaviors regarding their personal affective needs. After recruitment, resulting in ten participants, two virtual Zoom focus group sessions were scheduled and facilitated; two researchers moderated the focus group sessions, and five participants joined each focus group session. Each focus group session lasted for 90 minutes. Audio recordings of the focus group sessions were saved and transcribed for data analysis. The researchers shared the notes after the focus group sessions were completed and identified the emerging themes from both sessions together. Based on the consensus, the research team finalized the identified themes.

FINDINGS & DISCUSSION

Meditative gameplay and lighthearted mood

Depending on individual preferences, some participants preferred difficult games, while others said that games with a lighthearted atmosphere and a perceived high chance of success helps them to relax (e.g., Participant 1). Although most participants talked about easy or non-competitive games as relaxing games when asked, it should be noted that not all participants were the same. Playing strategy games that require a certain level of cognitive engagement could let some participants relax more than other types of games. Game players' preference for different cognitive and intellectual levels of difficulty echoes the previous findings from Lee *et al.* (2017).

“[...] it's not difficult, so you can kind of just like relax. Put some music on, and just like play the game without having to think too hard or try too hard. Also, like, I guess there's no chance of failure.”
(Participant 1)

Participants who preferred “easy” and “relaxing” games often mentioned games like *Animal Crossing: New Horizon* (2020), *Runescape* (2001), and *Stardew Valley* (2016). These games tend to have a “chill sandbox vibe,” which appealed to several participants in both focus groups. Members of our focus groups pointed to the beneficial impact of meditative gameplay on the player, as it helps them unwind and relax. This typically involves an opportunity to “turn your brain off” or escape from real circumstances into a state of repetitive gameplay or “grinding” that allows the player to let go of the anxiety of everyday life. As an example, participants pointed to in-game fishing and farming as repetitive low-stakes tasks that were appealing to them as ways to unwind and relax. They used the word “Zen” to describe the state of mind achieved by repetitive or meditative gameplay.

Sense of control, familiarity, and achievement

Sonnentag and Fritz (2007) identified individuals' sense of mastery and control as two of the major recovery experiences as they investigated how leisure activities can support mood regulation and job-stress recovery. Findings from our study confirmed their statement; several participants discussed their personalized experiences on mastery and control by playing video games.

“Let's say [you are] trying to do [the] careful, very specific maneuver in an environment to complete a goal, and you can keep doing it over again. You didn't get the right. You died here. What could I have done differently, and it's a distraction that gives you the illusion of [a] sense of control and the sense of accomplishment to that carry-on worked into reality.” (Participant 3)

Participant 3 links the sense of infinite chances to complete a goal and the opportunity to improve gradually over time with a sense of control. This constrained emotional “sandbox” in which to complete goals can be empowering because the goals in games are achievable and not limited by real-world constraints, unlike goals in real-life.

While some participants valued non-challenging repetitive tasks, other participants pointed to a challenging set of goals that are unrelated to the ones in their everyday lives. Although this could conceivably apply to infamously-hard games like *Dark Souls* (2011), *Elden Ring* (2022), or *Seikiro* (2019), participants in our focus groups focused on challenging aspects of simulation and strategy games as well as achieving goals with a group of players, like in MMORPGs (*Massively Multiplayer Online Role-Playing Games*). Participants explained that challenging strategy games, even when they reflected on real-world situations that were stressing the player, could still be helpful emotionally because the player had control over when to engage with the game.

“Maybe I mean partially, it’s probably because I’m still so, um, impacted by the coronavirus, so that [I am] playing a video game about a plague where everything is super hyper-controlled, and you can turn it off anytime you want if it gets too stressful.” (Participant 7, speaking about *Pathologic* by Ice-Pick Lodge)

Cathartic experiences

In-game morality—or the ethical intricacies of choices players make within games—was a subcategory of responses we received that is mostly outside the scope of this paper (e.g., participants deliberately initiating “bad” endings in games to get the trophies). However, one important element that players brought up within this framework is the cathartic and somewhat counterintuitive emotional power of horror games. The element of horror in games, and its unique cathartic appeal, have been discussed in previous game studies like Kirchhofer (2016), Gerarci *et al.* (2016), and Huntemann (2009), and findings from our study echo these. In our study, participants expressed that horror games could have transcendent moments and prescribed avenues for coping in a general sense. Participants also expressed that horror games offer relief from the stresses of their real lives because whatever was happening in a horror game was almost certainly worse than what was happening in their everyday lives.

“I was about fifteen, and my parents were getting divorced. Um, I was obsessed with the survival horror game called *Rule of Rose*, which is this really beautiful survival horror about a girl who finds herself in a strange and terrible place, and mostly it’s about trauma and accepting the past and sort of moving on from there. [...] But I think grief and sort of trauma are, sort of, you know, I think, very important elements of some video game stories. You’re not, I mean, you’re not going to get it with stuff like Pacman, right? But, um, you do get it with certain stories, and I think those do have a lot of therapeutic potentials.” (Participant 7)

Khoo (2012) found that an indirect cathartic experience through entertainment media helps to improve general health and psychological well-being. The author states, “reflecting on a human drama through cinema resulted in greater capacity at promoting catharsis by way of improving the individual’s self-efficacy in handling sad emotions” (p. 127). In our study, one participant also brought up games as a way of coping with and understanding grief.

“I had been playing it every so often called *Spiritfairer*, which is... Yeah, do you guys know about it? It’s for those who don’t know, it’s a game about like processing grief and accepting death. And so that honestly helped me a lot when I was going through that period, where it’s like, ‘I should appreciate the time I have with him now,’ and it just really helped me through the grieving process.” (Participant 6)

Findings in this study indicate that games, similar to cinematic entertainment experiences, may support one’s self-efficacy in regulating sadness. Games of this type may offer escapism as well as a sense of control derived from the linear narrative structure of the experience; the end result is already predetermined and, at times predictable, especially if the game has already been completed in previous playthroughs. Choosing to play such games and, by implication, searching for them would be a step toward mitigating negative feelings in this regard.

Gaming together VS. Solitary play

Our participants acknowledged the potential of multiplayer experiences to create a sense of community. The *Animal Crossing* and *World of Warcraft* series were two important examples that came up in our focus groups. One participant found the act of overcoming a “boss battle” with her guild members in *World of Warcraft* to be a transcendent experience that has ongoing resonance for her as a meaningful lifelong memory, even many years later. At the same time, others found *Animal Crossing: New Horizon* (2020) to be especially important as a means of finding community during the COVID-19 pandemic.

“I ended up playing with a group of other friends on like *Animal Crossing*, and a time I remember fondly is like there was a shooting star story night sort of thing going on, and we just all went to this one person’s island, all dressed up in our best, and we just watched the stars fall.” (Participant 6)

Acknowledging this, many of our participants who identified as female or non-binary noted the drawbacks of multiplayer experiences online, especially when they talked over voice chat and identified themselves as female. Others expressed apprehension about playing customizable multiplayer games with a female avatar for the same reason. Male participants similarly expressed apprehension about the “toxicity” of multiplayer games. They

acknowledged that female-presenting players are targeted, and also pointed to conflicts that arise when different communities clash in the gaming space. In these cases, game players felt more frustration and stress rather than having a sense of pleasure or stress-relieving experience, receiving the opposite outcome they had intended. In order to prevent these negative situations, participants talked about strategies for finding games that avoid certain groups or sticking to single-player games to avoid the problem altogether. The toxic online game environment and related cyberbullying have been well-researched in the existing studies, and some of the latest studies on this topic include Kwak *et al.* (2015), Beres *et al.* (2021), and Yildirim (2022). While the authors note that this is an important topic to investigate and improve the gaming environment, it is not in the scope of the current study.

Although the negative social aspects of online gameplay were discussed in our focus groups, participants also found meaning in communities around games as well as the games themselves. In some ways, this was a means to gain the benefits of multiplayer online experiences without being directly presented with the negative elements of online competitive play, such as participating in game forums or watching gameplay streaming videos.

Elements of solo-play that engage the player in expansive game worlds are important to improve mood or emotional outlook; participants described 1) engaging open-world settings where the player could get lost and 2) compelling narratives in both open-world and “telltale-type” games are good elements of explorative, immersive games that could enhance players’ moods. Also, 3) game achievements and collectibles participants can achieve makes these games compelling, as well as 4) the escapist element of engaging with a fictional online world that is still single-player. One participant expressed a similar interest in horror games because of the unconventional twists in the story, as well as the large number of collectibles available.

“[O]ne of my favorite games is *Until Dawn*, and it’s one of those interactive survival horror ones. [...] I got everything when I beat the game, I was like, ‘Man, I am the boss!’ [...] I was so elated because I’d gotten all those things and, [...] I just feel like really good about myself.” (Participant 4)

The gratifications of multiplayer and single-player video games have been discussed in previous studies, such as Barnett and Coulson (2010) and Lee *et al.* (2017). The consistent finding from the relevant video game literature and the current study is that each player has different game needs; different participants elevated their moods by either playing with their friends and family or enjoying solitary gameplay. It was certainly not one-size-fits-all. This indicates that providing more diverse options for selections and searches to users may be a fruitful direction for future retrieval and recommendation services to consider.

CONCLUSION

The current study used a focus group approach to understand the affective needs of video game players. Based on two virtual focus group sessions with ten participants, we have found that several different elements of video games can potentially support players to feel “better.” 1) Gameplay mechanics and style played an important role. For example, repetitive game elements produced an almost meditative response in the player, and similar gameplay activities helped players rest their minds. 2) Games with achievements and trophies helped players have a sense of control and achievement, which was often compared with real-life challenges that cannot easily be mastered or conquered like games. 3) Also, the narrative and world-building aspects of games supported players by providing cathartic experiences to help them cope with their struggles, like feeling grief. 4) Lastly, whether a game is multiplayer (seeking fellowship) or single-player (seeking solitary play) was a critical element to different game players, indicating individual preferences should be respected to support one’s emotional needs.

This study was conducted as a pilot study for a larger research project. Our research team plans to conduct in-depth semi-structured interviews to better understand individuals’ affective video game needs and how future information services can support them. While not investigated further in the current phase of the study, as one participant mentioned, there are different types of “feeling bad.” It can be sadness, depression, dealing with traumatic experiences, anxiety, and more. Future studies can look into different emotional challenges individuals have and understand which aspects of elements of games can potentially support regulating their moods—or trigger adverse reactions—for enhanced retrieval and recommendation services. In addition, games with physical activities and more sensory stimulations involved might be another worthwhile aspect to investigate to see if they could support individuals’ mood regulation.

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REFERENCES

Barnett, J., & Coulson, M. (2010). Virtually real: A psychological perspective on massively multiplayer online games. *Review of General Psychology*, 14(2), 167-179.

- Beres, N. A., Frommel, J., Reid, E., Mandryk, R. L., & Klarkowski, M. (2021, May). Don't you know that you're toxic: Normalization of toxicity in online gaming. In *Proceedings of the 2021 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems* (pp. 1-15).
- Dahlquist, L. M., Weiss, K. E., Dillinger, L., Law, E. F., Ackerman, C. S., & McKenna, K. D. (2009). Effects of videogame distraction using a virtual reality type head-mounted display helmet on cold pressor pain in children. *Journal of Pediatric Psychology, 34*(5), 574–584. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jpepsy/jsn023>
- Geraci, R. M., Recine, N., & Fox, S. (2016). Grotesque gaming: the monstrous in online worlds. *Preternature: Critical and Historical Studies on the Preternatural, 5*(2), 213-236.
- Glavin, C. E. Y., & Montgomery, P. (2017). Creative bibliotherapy for post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD): A systematic review. *Journal of Poetry Therapy, 30*(2), 95–107. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08893675.2017.1266190>
- Gross, J. J. (2014). *Handbook of emotion regulation* (2nd ed.). The Guilford Press.
- Huntemann, N. B. (2009). Playing with fear: Catharsis and resistance in military-themed video games. In *Joystick Soldiers* (pp. 239-252). Routledge.
- Kirchhofer, G. (2016). *Why Are Horror Games Appealing?*. Anchor Academic Publishing.
- Khoo, G. S. (2012). *The Therapeutic Effects of Cinema: An Experimental Study of Catharsis through Narrative Media and Contemplation*. [Doctoral dissertation, Pennsylvania State University]. https://etda.libraries.psu.edu/files/final_submissions/7676
- Kwak, H., Blackburn, J., & Han, S. (2015, April). Exploring cyberbullying and other toxic behavior in team competition online games. In *Proceedings of the 33rd annual ACM conference on human factors in computing systems* (pp. 3739-3748).
- Lee, J., Lee, J., Lim, H., Son, J. S., Lee, J. R., Kim, D. C., & Ko, S. (2012). Cartoon distraction alleviates anxiety in children during induction of anesthesia. *Anesthesia & Analgesia, 115*(5), 1168–1173. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0b013e31824fb469>.
- Lee, J. H., Clarke, R. I., Cho, H., & Windleharth, T. (2017). Understanding Appeals of Video Games for Reader's Advisory and Recommendation. *Reference & User Services Quarterly, 57*(2), 127-139.
- Patel, A., Schieble, T., Davidson, M., Tran, M. C., Schoenberg, C., Delphin, E., & Bennett, H. (2006). Distraction with a hand-held video game reduces pediatric preoperative anxiety. *Pediatric Anesthesia, 16*(10), 1019–1027. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-9592.2006.01914.x>
- Peterkin, A., & Grewal, S. (2017). Bibliotherapy: The therapeutic use of fiction and poetry in mental health. *International Journal of Person Centered Medicine, 7*(3), 175–181. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1351-0126.2001.00428.x>
- Reinecke, L., & Rieger, D. (2020). Media Entertainment as a Self-Regulatory Resource. In *The Oxford Handbook of Entertainment Theory*.
- Rubin, L. C. (Ed.). (2020). *Using superheroes and villains in counseling and play therapy: A guide for mental health professionals*. Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Russoniello, C. V., Fish, M., & O'Brien, K. (2013). The efficacy of casual videogame play in reducing clinical depression: a randomized controlled study. *GAMES FOR HEALTH: Research, Development, and Clinical Applications, 2*(6), 341–346. <https://doi.org/10.1089/g4h.2013.0010>
- Sonnentag, S., & Fritz, C. (2007). The recovery experience questionnaire: Development and validation of a measure for assessing recuperation and unwinding from work. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology, 12*(3), 204–221. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1076-8998.12.3.204>
- Yıldırım, N. (2022). The Bullying Game: Sexism Based Toxic Language Analysis on Online Games Chat Logs by Text Mining. *Journal of International Women's Studies, 24*(3), 7.